

Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Trivalent Gadolinium, Yttrium, Terbium, Dysprosium and Holmium Complexes with 2-(*p*-sulphophenylazo) 1, 8-dihydroxynaphthalene 3, 6 disulphonic Acid (Trisodium salt) [Spadns]

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IN continuation with the work reported¹ from these laboratories on the complexation reactions of SPADNS with La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III), the work has been further extended with other lanthanides. The stepwise stability constant of Gd(III), Y(III), Tb(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) complexes with SPADNS have been determined potentiometrically in aqueous solution using Bjerrum-Calvin technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti at different temperatures (20° and 40°) and 0.1M ionic strength (NaClO₄). The trend in the stability of these metal complexes has been found to be :

The overall changes in ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° accompanying the complex formation have also been determined.

Experimental

Solutions of metal nitrates Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III), (BDH, Anala R Grade) were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantities in conductivity water. The solution of yttrium perchlorate was prepared from Y₂O₃ by the method as reported earlier¹. All the solutions were standardized by oxalate method². The experimental procedures were the same as reported

earlier¹. pH measurements recorded with a Phillips pH meter (PR 9405M) with glass and calomel electrodes at 20° and 40° (maintained in a thermostat). The instrument was calibrated using buffer tablets of pH 4 and 7.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constants of SPADNS and stepwise stability constants of its complexes with lanthanides were determined using Calvin-Bjerrum^{3,4} technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁵. The values of proton-ligand stability constants were found to be in close agreement with the values reported earlier¹.

The metal-ligand formation constant values were determined using the following techniques :

(i) Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values^{3,4}, (ii) Least square treatment^{6,7} (Curve-fitting method) and (iii) Pointwise calculations method. The final values of $\log K_1$ are given in Table 1.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG°) enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) accompanying complex formation have been determined using the standard equations⁸. The values of thermodynamic parameters are also given in Table 1.

From a comparative account of the stability constants it is evident that values are slightly higher at 20° as compared to 40°, indicating that low temperature is favourable for complex formation. The trend in the stability of metal complexes is Ho(III) > Dy(III) > Tb(III) > Y(III) > Gd(III) at 20° and 40°, which is in agreement with accepted view that the stability of lanthanide complexes increases with their decrease in ionic radii.

Lanthanides-SPADNS complex formation is a spontaneous process which is evident from the more negative values of ΔG° with increase in temperature. The negative values of ΔH° ensures that the reaction is exothermic. The positive values of ΔS° indicate that entropy factor is favourable for the complex formation.

TABLE 1 — METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Metal ion used	$\log K_1$		ΔG° (K.Cal.mol ⁻¹)		$-\Delta H^\circ$ (K.Cal.mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (Cal/mol/C)
	20°C	40°C	20°C	40°C		
Gd ³⁺	8.73	8.46	12.15	11.85	7.84	15.87
Y ³⁺	8.91	8.64	12.35	12.05	8.67	17.90
Tb ³⁺	9.06	8.87	12.85	12.45	10.02	18.15
Dy ³⁺	9.17	8.95	13.05	12.85	11.11	18.85
Ho ³⁺	9.32	9.12	13.25	12.97	11.67	19.10

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Studies on Se(IV) and Te(IV) Dithiocarbamates

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A perusal of literature shows that scarcely attempts have been made earlier for the study of the aforesaid metal dithiocarbamates¹⁻³. In continuation of our work on Tellurium(IV)⁴ here we report infra-red and thermogravimetric measurements of Se(IV) and Te(IV) complexes of morpholine, piperidine and pyrrolidine dithiocarbamates.

Experimental

Potassium salts of the dithiocarbamates were prepared according to the procedure reported in the literature⁵. The solution of selenium dioxide and potassium tellurite was prepared in distilled water.

Preparation of the Complexes (General Method) :

To a solution of metal(IV) ions (0.1M) in water (20 ml.) was added with stirring the solution (0.1M) of

the potassium salt of the reagent in water (100 ml.). The precipitate was digested on steam-bath for 10 minutes. The complex was filtered, washed with water, finally with ether and dried at 110°-120°.

Results and Discussion

The tellurium(IV) complexes start to lose weight (moisture) at around 90° and completed at 100°. The anhydrous dithiocarbamates decompose sharply at temperature ranging 160-260° [Te(mdtc)₄], 158-250° [Te(pipdtc)₄], and 126-290° [Te(pydtc)₄]. The organic matter completely oxidised at the highest temperature of the aforesaid ranges thereafter a stable region ranging 260-340°, 250-400°, and 290-360°, respectively. In these ranges the formation of tellurium sulphide is concluded which finally oxidised to tellurium oxide. The % of loss in weight observed for different products formed during the heating almost coincide with the % of loss in weight calculated. The DTA confirm the results obtained from TGA

The selenium complexes become anhydrous after losing their moisture around 60°. The decomposition of selenium dithiocarbamates of morpholine, piperidine and pyrrolidine start at 150°, 150° and 130° and completed at 280°, 260° and 300° respectively, thereafter a stable region upto 300°, 320° and 400° which is due to the formation of selenium sulphide. The final product of oxidation is selenium oxide. The DTA supports the observation of TGA.

Results of the TGA curves of the complexes (heating rate 5° min⁻¹) indicate that the complexes of morpholine and piperidine dithiocarbamates with the aforesaid ions are thermally more stable than the pyrrolidine dithiocarbamates. The temperatures at which the complex starts decomposition are lower in case of Se(IV) complexes than the Te(IV) complexes. The rigid morpholine ring to release the electron might be a cause of higher decomposition temperature than the piperidine and pyrrolidine dithiocarbamates complexes.

The assignment for the C-N and C-S stretching frequencies for the complexes are listed in Table-1. The bands in the region 1000-990 cm⁻¹ for the latter and 1480-1470 cm⁻¹ for the former. The C-N mode for diethyl-dithiocarbamate is at 1477 cm⁻¹ compared to 1438 cm⁻¹ - 1445 cm⁻¹ for aforesaid dithiocarbamates. This suggest that there is less double bond character in carbon-nitrogen bond. In all the complexes the ligand shows a bidentate nature. It has been reported earlier that complexes having bidentate R₂NCS₂ group exhibit a single ν(C-N) and a ν(C-S)